

THE PREPARATION OF HALOGEN-SUBSTITUTED PHENYLACETIC ACIDS

BY G. S. MISRA AND J. S. SHUKLA

A method for the preparation of the chloro- and bromo-phenylacetic acids has been described.

A general method for the preparation of all the halogeno-phenylacetic acids has been developed by Campbell and McKail (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1251) by the application of Gränacher's synthesis (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 610; 1923, 6, 458). The course of the reaction is represented as follows:

This method of conversion of the benzaldehydes into the phenylacetic acids involves five steps, though the overall yields are stated to be good. Apart from this rhodanine, which is used in this reaction, can be prepared only with some difficulty.

o-Bromophylacetic acid has been prepared by Fieser and Kilmer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1356) by the application of Arndt-Eistert synthesis. This method is of general application and gives reasonably good yields, but is limited by the slow formation of the intermediate diazo-ketones and the difficulty of working with diazomethane (cf. Campbell and McKail, *loc. cit.*). Other methods of preparation (cf. Bedson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1880, 37, 94; Kindler and Peschke, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1933, 271, 435; Kindler and Gehlhaar, *ibid.*, 1936, 274, 377 *et seq.*) have been reviewed by Campbell and McKail (*loc. cit.*) but are not found to be very successful.

An alternative route to the preparation of halogen-substituted phenylacetic acids from the corresponding substituted toluenes has recently become available. It has been shown by Schmid and Karrer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, 29, 573) that when toluene is reacted upon by *N*-bromosuccinimide in the presence of a small quantity of benzoyl peroxide as a catalyst, benzyl bromide is formed in good yield. By the application of this method a large number of substituted benzyl bromides have been prepared from the corresponding toluenes (Misra and Shukla, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 277; cf. Djerassi, *Chem. Rev.*, 1948, 43, 271). The yields are reasonably good, viz., 84, 73, and 76% for the *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloro-, and 69, 55 and 64% for the corresponding bromo-benzyl bromides, respectively. The benzyl bromides were converted into the phenylacetonitriles, which on hydrolysis afforded the phenylacetic acids. The course of the reaction has been formulated as below and involves only three steps from the toluene to the phenylacetic acid:

The phenylacetonitriles were obtained in yields of 61, 83 and 71% for the *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloro- and 60, 61 and 77% in the case of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-bromo- substituted compounds respectively. For the hydrolysis of the phenylacetonitriles to the phenylacetic acids a mixture of equal volumes of concentrated sulphuric acid, glacial acetic acid and water was found to be quite satisfactory (cf. Campbell and McKail, *loc. cit.*). In this way the phenylacetic acids were prepared in yields of 89, 91 and 89% for the *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloro- and 98, 91, and 95% for the corresponding *o*-, *m*- and *p*-bromo- substituted compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Phenylacetonitriles

o-Chlorophenylacetonitrile.—*o*-Chlorobenzyl bromide (40 g.) was added to a solution of sodium cyanide (12 g.) in hot water (15 c.c.) and ethanol (20 c.c.) during the course of about 10 minutes. The mixture was then boiled for 3 hours longer, cooled and filtered, and the ethanol was distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue was then distilled in vacuum. *o*-Chlorophenylacetonitrile was collected at 115°/9mm., yield 18 g. (61%). (Lit., b.p. 123°-125°/11 mm.).

m-Chlorophenylacetonitrile was similarly prepared from *m*-chlorobenzyl bromide (5 g.) and potassium cyanide (2 g.), dissolved in water (5 c.c.) and ethanol (5 c.c.). It was collected at 127°/7 mm., yield 3 g. (83%). (Lit., b.p. 134°-136°/10 mm.).

p-Chlorophenylacetonitrile was prepared in the same way from *p*-chlorobenzyl bromide (15 g.) and potassium cyanide (6 g.), dissolved in water (10 c.c.) and ethanol (10 c.c.). It was collected at 140°/10 mm., yield 7.8 g. (71%). (Lit., b.p., 137°-139°/12 mm.).

o-Bromophenylacetonitrile was similarly prepared from *o*-bromobenzyl bromide (3 g.) and potassium cyanide (2 g.), dissolved in water (5 c.c.) and ethanol (5 c.c.), b.p. 131°-132°/8mm., yield 1.4 g. (60%). (Lit., b.p. 140°-141°/13 mm.).

m-Bromophenylacetonitrile was prepared from *m*-bromobenzyl bromide (2.5 g.) and potassium cyanide (2 g.), dissolved in water (5 c.c.) and ethanol (5 c.c.). It was collected at 140°-142°/8mm., yield 1.2 g. (61%). (Lit., b.p. 145°-147°/10 mm.).

p-Bromophenylacetonitrile was prepared from *p*-bromobenzyl bromide (5 g.) and potassium cyanide (3 g.), dissolved in water (5 c.c.) and ethanol (5 c.c.), b.p. 142°/5 mm., yield 3 g. (77%). (Lit., b.p. 152°-156°/10-12 mm.).

Preparation of Phenylacetic Acids

o-Chlorophenylacetic Acid.—*o*-Chlorophenylacetonitrile (5 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of equal volumes (5 c.c. each) of concentrated sulphuric acid, glacial acetic acid and water. The reaction was complete in about an hour, when the mixture was poured in excess of water. *o*-Chlorophenylacetic acid, which separated out, had a

m.p. 93-94° (lit., m.p. 96°), yield 5 g. (89%). (Found: Equiv., 170.1. Calc. for $C_8H_7O_2Cl$: Equiv., 170.5).

m-Chlorophenylacetic Acid.—*m*-Chlorophenylacetonitrile (4 g.) was hydrolysed as above, m.p. of acid, 76° (lit., m.p. 76° yield 4.1 g. (91%). (Found: Equiv., 171. Calc. for $C_8H_7O_2Cl$: Equiv., 170.5).

p-Chlorophenylacetic Acid.—*p*-Chlorophenylacetonitrile (7 g.) was hydrolysed as above, m.p. of acid, 104-105° (lit., m.p. 105°), yield 7 g. (89%). (Found: Equiv., 169.4. Calc. for $C_8H_7O_2Cl$: Equiv., 170.5).

o-Bromophenylacetic acid was similarly prepared from the hydrolysis of *o*-bromophenylacetonitrile (1.4 g.) and after crystallisation from light petroleum (b.p. 80-100°) melted at 104°-105° (lit., 105°-106°), yield 1.5 g. (98%). (Found: Equiv., 215. Calc. for $C_8H_7O_2Br$: Equiv., 215).

m-Bromophenylacetic acid was similarly obtained from the hydrolysis of *m*-bromophenylacetonitrile (1 g.). After crystallisation from hot water, m.p. was 99-101° (lit., m.p. 100°), yield 1 g. (91%). (Found: Equiv., 216. Calc. for $C_8H_7O_2Br$: Equiv., 215).

p-Bromophenylacetic acid was obtained from the hydrolysis of *p*-bromophenylacetonitrile (2.5 g.) as above, m.p. 113-14° (lit., m.p. 114°), yield 2.6 g. (95%). (Found: Equiv., 216. Calc. for $C_8H_7O_2Br$: Equiv., 215).

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received March 22, 1951.